

Probiotic Formula That Support Oral Health

Dental caries is a multifactorial disease. Its pathogenesis involves the microbiota, the host, its immune mechanisms, and the diet. Even though all these factors have to intervene for dental caries to develop, microbiological factors are still the leading cause of this disease.

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Debridement treatment of dental caries can be surgical or non-surgical, and in some cases, systemic administration of antimicrobials is required. As a type of bacteriotherapy, probiotics can decrease CFU counts of cariogenic pathogens. The mechanism of probiotics in the oral cavity is not clearly established. They are associated with decreased CFU counts of cariogenic pathogens and the inhibition of periodontal pathogens. They also modulate the inflammatory response (humoral and cellular) and produce substances such as lactic acid, hydrogen peroxide and bacteriocins (antimicrobial agents produced by lactic acid bacteria, whose action provides them probiotic effect).

Product List

Creative Enzymes provides high-quality oral health formula for academic and industrial use. Please contact us for product details.

Cat No.	Product Name	Activity	Appearance
PBOH-003	Probiotics Blend for Oral Health	10 billion CFU/g or more	White to Light Yellow-Colored, Free-Flowing Powder
PRBT-020	Lactobacillus Helveticus Freeze Dried Powder	10 billion CFU/g or more	White to Light Yellow-Colored, Free-Flowing Powder
PRBT-021	Lactobacillus Paracasei Freeze Dried Powder	10 billion CFU/g or more	White to Light Yellow-Colored, Free-Flowing Powder
PRBT-025	Lactobacillus Salivarius Freeze Dried Powder	10 billion CFU/g or more	White to Light Yellow-Colored, Free-Flowing Powder

Creative Enzymes also provides other probiotic products with multiple functions in addition to the ones listed above. Please [contact us](#) for any needs.

Note: Our products can only be used for the purpose of research and industrial production, not for individual use.

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